

THE INFLUENCE OF THE CLUB'S INFRASTRUCTURE ON THE SOCCER COACHING PROCESS: EVIDENCE FROM THE CLUB REPRESENTATIVE LONGITUDINAL SURVEY

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Abstract:

The objective of this study was to investigate the impact of facilities and equipment in the coaching processes of soccer practical session and also indicate the ways of intervention to the problem. This study was conducted on the Aba Buna sport club, Jimma. The data was collected from primary and secondary sources, which include qualitative and quantitative research method for the purposive. The sample size for the study includes 28 players and 2 coaches. The necessary information had collected through questionnaires which included both open ended and closed ended questions. There were twelve questions in each questionnaire for the players and coaches as well. Only one question is open ended. One week was given to filled questionnaire. The result of study indicates, the facilities and equipment have an exerted impact to improve and develop the efficiency of the clubs practical session. However, the club has intending to solve such problem and solve inadequacy facility equipment is left the club. Therefore, according to this identified result research forward recommendation to overcome the problem.

Keywords: facilities, equipment, coaching processes, soccer

1. Introduction

Soccer is one of the wide spread sport activity throughout the word. This is due to it is nature and the importance the game for physical improvement. In addition, the game is

preferable for all age level, sex and without including, colors, races environment, religion etc. (Lenin son and Charistenser 1996). Burcher and Bening (1974) stated that the proper execution of appropriate coaching method involved consideration of several factors as clubs size, equipment and facilities. Facilities and equipment in soccer are not such expensive that they can prepared where ever small space is available.

E Pearson (1958) stated that a coaching program can be greatly inhibited by absence of adequate facilities equipment and supplies. Coaching should be frustrated by the lack of facilities. Quality coaching and facilities will contribute positively to player development. Previous research has shown that the quality of athletic facilities has a significant effect on player attitudes. For example, Pujals and Vieira (2002) found that poor club infrastructure may cause feelings of failure and pessimism in soccer players, leading to a lack of motivation. In the Unites States, the quality of athletic facilities is an important factor influencing high school athletes in their college choice (Letawsky, Schneider, Pedersen, & Palmer, 2003). Anecdotal evidence suggests that the infrastructure of soccer clubs is an important factor in the development of successful players (Corrêa, Alchieri, Duarte, & Strey, 2002). Since, player development is the backbone of the game. The availability of facilities and equipment are the part of both long term and short term planning.

The development and achievement of any sports basically depends upon the facilities and equipment. Sport facilities and equipment have a great impact in coaching process with both coach and players. Omoruan (1996) posited that facilities and equipment are the greatest among all factors that affect the growth of a sport. The fulfillment of facilities and equipment make coaching method precise towards the achievement of desire goal. Ogbemudia (2001) emphasized that if Nigeria must attain the desired standards in performance and attain top ratings in the Olympic Games, then the planning and management of sports facilities and equipment must not only be broad based but also be backed-up with adequate provision and maintenance of the available facilities and equipment. According to Talabi (1998), the attainment of a world class status in sports is a reflection of the presence of top standard equipment and facilities. He added that most developed countries are putting so much stress into building excellent facilities and providing standard equipment as well as creating conducive environments for their athletes. According to Ekpe (2001), it is difficult to separate the standard of sports in a country from the standard of facilities and equipment available.

Generally, the use of facilities and equipment by the participant is strongly encouraged or sometimes enforces to minimize the risk of injury. The sporting equipment and environment need to be designs main tend and inspected regularly to

ensure the participants safety and wellbeing are created far equipment which makes completion judging and eagling results more accurate and more easing the opportunities to access quality playing conditions for both new and existing players. (S.A Harry and W.B. Richard 1958). There is plenty of space, but the quality of the fields varies a lot. While there are a lot of soccer parks sprouting up around the country, the facilities vary widely. Many fields are overused, both by soccer teams alone and by others sports that may share them. Due to wide varying climatic condition in many parts of the country, fields are difficult to maintain. Often fields are in park s where there are no changing facilities. While there are some difficulties, facilities and equipment are certainly available for soccer team. However, to select the appropriate method of coaching the coacher must consider factor that affect the method of the coaching while formulating and implementing instructional techniques.

The main objective of this study was to investigate the impact of facilities and equipment in the coaching processes of soccer practical session and also indicate the ways of intervention to the problem. Soccer is given in the club under the study with absolute insufficiencies of facilities and equipment.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Study designs

The study was designed to identify the impact of facility and equipment in coaching process of soccer practical session a case of Aba Buna football club, Jimma. This research was used both quantitative and qualitative research design.

2.2 Source of data

The study was used both primary and secondary source of data to investigate the problem, the questionnaire was used as a primary source and for secondary sources relevant literature were used.

2.3 Sampling size and sampling techniques

The sample size for the study was about 28 players and 2 coaches due to the limited number of players and coaches in the club. Because of this small number the researcher used purposive sample technique.

Table1: Age and gender description of the players & Coach

Sr. No.	Alternatives age group	Players		Coach	
		No	Percentage (%)	No	Percentage (%)
1	13-16	5	17.85	0	0
2	17-20	7	25.00	0	0
3	21-25	10	35.71	0	0
4	25-30	6	21.41	1	50
5	Above 30	0	0	1	50
	Total	28	100	2	100

2.4 Data collection Instrument

The necessary information was collected through questionnaires. The researcher developed and validates a questionnaire with the help of experts in physical education and sports science field. The questions were revolving around the impact of facilities and equipment in coaching process of soccer practical session. The questionnaire was process in number of closed and open ended questions.

2.5 Data collection procedures

The questionnaire and observations technique were used for the collection of relevant information to check whether a problem is really exist or not and to evaluate whether it is solved or minimized after intervention. Firstly, questionnaires were distributed to coaches and players. All the necessary information was provided in details on the front page of questionnaire. One week was given to fill the questionnaire.

2.6 Method of data analysis

Data were analysis and interprets in terms of percentage followed by table and graphs. The quantitative and qualitative analysis procedures were also used to conclude as well as for recommendation.

3. Result

The result was elaborate here under two different subs heading as follows:

A. Analysis of Responses from the Players

1. Question resulted to method of coaching for the player.

Table 2

Item - 1	Alternative coaching method	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Most of the time exercising the way of coaching style in your football teams?	Technical	5	17.85
	Tactical	10	35.71
	Both	13	46.4
	Total	28	100

Table 2 indicates that about 13(46.4%) of the respondents replied that the 5(17.85%) technical and the remaining 10.(35.71%) tactical way of coaching style. This implies the coaching process is more of focuses and both individual and group ability and most of players are interested for technical and tactical way of coaching style.

2. Question related to the level of implementing modern equipment's for soccer coaches

Table 3

Item - 2	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
How do you rate the effects of the coach to improving the modern equipment with local materials?	Very high	6	21.42
	High	6	21.42
	Low	9	32.14
	Average	7	25
	Total	28	100

According to the table 3 about 6 (21.42%) of respondents replied that there is very high level of using modern equipment's of soccer in practical training whereas 21.42 % said there is high level of using modern equipment. The 32.14% side that there is low of using modern equipment and also 2(7.1%) of the respondents is said that average. So the fulfillment of equipment for coaching is that much for coaching.

3. Question related to shortage of facility and equipment.

Table 4

Item - 3	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Do you think the impact of facility and equipment affects your motivation?	Yes	17	60.7
	No	11	39.3
	Total	28	100

According to table 4 indicate that 17(60.7%) of ensure that inadequacy of facility and equipment affect the player participation whereas 11(39.3%) ensure that in adequately of facility and equipment not create problem of player participation.

4. Question related of proportion of ball and cone with player

Table 5

Item - 4	Alternative	Number of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Are you satisfied in training facilities of ball and cone with player is?	Yes	12	42.85
	No	16	57.15
	Total	28	100

According to table 5 indicate that 12(42.85%) response the preparation of ball and cone satisfied whereas 16(57.15%) the proportion of ball and cone is not appropriate with the number of players.

5. Question related with the extent to which facilities and equipment's are utilized in soccer training.

Table 6

Item - 5	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
At what extent equipment are utilized in your football training?	Very high	6	21.72
	High	6	21.72
	Low	6	21.72
	average	10	35.74
	Total	28	100

According to the table 6 about 6 (21.72%) respondents said that instruments utilized as very high level about 6 (21.72%) respondents says high level and the rest 6 (21.72%) have responded equipment are utilized at low level on their soccer training and 10 (35.74%) respondent the equipment utilizes is enough. This indicated the equipment are utilize significantly in training program in sufficient manner.

6. Question related to facility and equipment in training practical session.

Table 7

Item - 6	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Do you believe that the impact of facility and equipment affect your club result	Yes	15	53.57
	No	13	46.43
	Total	28	100

According to the above table 7 about 15(53.57%) of the respondents are believed that the availability of facility and equipment have a significant impact on their effectiveness, whereas 13(46.42 %) of the respondents believes that availability of facilities and equipment have no significant impact on their effectiveness.

7. Question related to with attention of coaches during practical session with facilities and equipment which are available in the club.

Table 8

Item - 7	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Does your coach give attention if availability of facilities of facilities and equipment which are exist in the club?	Yes	19	64.85
	No	9	32.15
	Total	28	100

According to the above table 8 about 19 (64.85%) respondents says that there is a good attention of coaches of available equipment and facilities supporting practices of soccer training only 9 (32.15%) of the respondents imply that are not sure about at the attention of coaches towards the facilities and equipment necessary to their training.

8. Question related with replacement of soccer equipment by local equipment.

Table 9

Item - 8	Alternative	Number of respondent	Percentage (%)
Do you believe that modern equipment replaced by local available materials?	Yes	23	82.15
	No	5	17.85
	Total	28	100

According to the table 9 about 23 (85.15%) respondent that modern facilities and equipment can easily replace by local available materials, about 5 (17.85%) respondents are not believed that modern equipment replace by local made materials. This implies there is a positive attitude towards homemade (domestic) equipment can easily avoid by local materials.

9. Question related to the impact of facilities and equipment in adequacy on the coaching process of soccer.

Table 10

Item - 9	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Does impact of the inadequacy of equipment and facilities on coaching process?	Make as players passive	7	25
	Problems on training	12	42.86
	all	9	32.14
	Total	28	100

As above Table 10 indicate that 7 (25%) respondents that inadequacy of facility create problem on participation and make problems on training whereas 12 (42.86%) ensure that in inadequacy of equipment create both make as players passive and problem on training.

10. Question related to the rate to solve the shortage of equipment's.

Table 11

Item - 10	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Whose is the role is to solve shortage of equipment's?	Clubs responsibility	28	100
	Coach	.0	0
	Players	.0	0
	Total	28	100

According to the table 11, all respondents i.e. 28 (100%) agree to the role to solve shortage of equipment is clubs responsibilities.

11. Question related to the rate to the satisfaction proportion of ball in training session?

Table 12

Item - 11	Alternative	Number of respondent	Percentage (%)
Satisfied the proportion of ball in training session?	Yes	15	53.57
	No	13	46.43
	Total	28	100

According to the above table 12 about 15 (53.57%) respondents believed that they are satisfied with the ball in training session, whereas 13 (46.42 %) respondents believes that they are not satisfied with the ball in training session.

12. Question:-Do you have other impact in practical session of soccer mention it?

The open ended question raise for players regarding other problems on coaching process of soccer, they were mention:

- Lack of fast medication when the injury is happen, such as physiotherapy
- Lack of sport drink during training session like high land water etc...
- Lack of shower source after training
- Lakes of training shirts are the open-ended question response of players.

B. ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM THE COACHES

1. Characteristics of the coaches' experience.

Table 13

No	Years of experience	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	1-5	1	50
2	6-10	1	50
3	11-15	-	-
4	>15	-	-
	Total	2	100

The table indicates that about 1 (50%) coach have 1-5 year experienced in coaching whereas other coach found experience between 6-10 years.

2. Question related method of coaching for the players.

Table 14

Item-2	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Alternative of coaching method	Tactical	-	-
	Technical	1	50
	Both equally	1	50
	Total	2	100

According to the table above about 1 (50%) of the coach response that the coaching method they used are technical and the other 1 (50%) coach is used technical as well as tactical coaching method.

3. Question the extent to which players are motivated in the training session.

Table 15

Item - 3	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
At what extent your players are interested to attend football practical session	Very high	-	-
	High	2	100%
	Average	-	-
	Low	-	-
	Total	2	100

The above table indicates that, 100% respondents are interested to attend soccer practical session at high level.

4. Question related to proportion of equipment (ball) to the players.

Table 16

Item - 4	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
The proportion of equipment (ball) with the player's number is?	Very high	1	50
	High	1	50
	Average	-	-
	Low	-	-
	Total	2	100

According to the table about 1of the respondent said that they have very high proportion of materials for players whereas the other 1 (50%) said that it is high level the proportion of equipment (ball) with the number of players.

5. Question related on believes that impacts of facilities and equipment affect your club results.

Table 17

Item - 5	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Do you believe that impact of facilities and equipment affects your club results	Yes	2	100
	No	-	-
	Total	2	100

According to the above table 2 participants' response is that the impact of facilities and equipment affects the club results.

6. Question related to the extent to which facilities and equipment utilized.

Table 18

Item – 6	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
The extent to which facility and equipment are utilized?	Very high	-	
	High	2	100
	Average	-	-
	Low	-	-
	Total	2	100

According to above table 100 of respondent do response that the extents to which facilities and equipment are utilized as 'high', this implies there is a good level utilization of equipment.

7. Question related to the responsibility to prepare the equipment and facilities which serving on coaching players during training session.

Table 19

Item – 7	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Who is responsible to prepare the equipment and facilities which serving on coaching players during training session	Coach	-	-
	Players	-	-
	Others	2	100
	Total	2	100

As the above table shows the responsibility to prepare the equipment and facilities which serving on training is for is for other on the 2(100%) response.

8. Question related to discussion about clubs problem of training

Table 20

Item – 8	Alternative	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Do you discuss about your club problem with your player out of training	Yes	2	100
	No	-	-
	Total	2	100

As the above table shows that, the all coaches discuss about clubs problem with their players out of the training.

9. Question related to the assumption that replaced the modern soccer equipment y home material.

Table 21

Item – 9	Alternative	Numbers of Respondents	Percentage (%)
If it possible to replace modern material by local available materials	Yes	2	100
	No	-	-
	Total	2	100

As the above table shows that, there are possibilities to replace modern soccer equipment with local available materials.

10. Question related to the role to solve the shortage of facilities and equipment

Table – 22

Item – 10	Alternative	Numbers of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Whose role is to solve, the shortage of equipment and facilities of club?	Clubs responsibility	2	100
	Coach	-	-
	Player	-	-
	Total	2	100

The results state that this is the club responsibility to solve the shortage of equipment and facility.

11. If you have any other problem regarding on coaching process of soccer practical session mention it?

The open ended question raised for coaches, to suggest the reason for the shortage of equipment therefore suggests that:

- As a club the role to solve such problem is clubs responsibility
- There is no other body to solve such problem.
- To compute with other the club should fulfill the materials.
- The open ended question raised for coaches, related to any other problem
- Regarding coaching process of soccer. They suggested that:
- Lack of training material for training such as cone, shirts, balls etc.
- Lack of medication when the injury is happen.

- Conflict each other, during training session.

4. Conclusion

The questions that were assumed reflect attitude of coaches and players were analyzed in detail, according to the data analysis the following major conclusion were drawn.

1. Equipment and facilities affects the coaching process of practical session in the club, in this regard the result of this research shows that the equipment and facilities plays a major role in modification of players performance reverse these are not enough and not properly accessed to each players which makes some difficulty to conduct the training smoothly.
2. Most of the respondents believe that modern equipment can replaced by local available equipment, so the club can use locale equipment to reduce in adequacy of equipment and facilities in the club. Even though they can reduce their expanse because local equipment's are very cheap relative to modern equipment.
3. Inadequacies of facilities and equipment have adverse impact on players' participants and practical coaching process.
4. Generally as the research result shows the club is the only channel, to fulfill inadequacy of equipment and facilities, so the club should work hard to solve the problem especially focus own to have different cone, training shirt , highland ,shower house and medication (physiotherapy).

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